

1,3-Dipolar Cycloaddition of Diphenyl Nitrile Imine with 4-Arylmethylene-2,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2-phenyl/phenylmethyl-3H-pyrazol-3-ones

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1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reactions have been studied to a numerous unsaturated systems leading to five-membered ring heterocycles¹⁻³. 4-Arylmethylene-2,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2-phenyl/phenylmethyl-3H-pyrazol-3-ones (1a-d; as dipolarophile) reacted with diphenylnitrileimine (2; as 1,3-dipole) to yield two isomers, viz. *E*- and *Z*-4,5-dihydrospiro-[4-aryl-1,3-diphenylpyrazole-5,4'-(2',4'-dihydro-5'-methyl-2'-phenyl/phenylmethyl-3'-H-pyrazol-3'-ones)] (3a-d and 4a-d respectively). The diphenylnitrileimine (2) is generated *in situ* by the reaction of phenylhydrazonoyl chloride and triethylamine in the presence of dry chloroform at room temperature. The physical and spectral data of the compounds are presented (Table 1).

- a; R=CH₂Ph, X=*p*-OMe
- b; R=CH₂Ph, X=*p*-NMe₂
- c; R=Ph, X=*p*-OMe
- d; R=Ph, X=*p*-NMe₂

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Büchi apparatus and are uncorrected. Microanalyses were carried out on a Coleman C, H and N analysers. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 720 and 257 spectrophotometers and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on Varian A-60D and Jeol FX-90Q spectrometers using TMS as an internal standard.

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 4

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	$\nu_{\max}$ cm^{-1}	δ
3a	70	185-6	1 730s (C=O), 1 610s (C=N)	1.34 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.78 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.92 (2H, AB q, J _{AB} 12.0 Hz, CH ₂), 5.30 (1H, s, CH), 6.70-7.60 (19H, m, ArH)
4a	30	163-5	1 725s (C=O), 1 610s (C=N)	2.08 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.80 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.60 (2H, s, CH ₂), 5.00 (1H, s, CH), 6.76-7.60 (19H, m, ArH)
3b	60	199-200	1 710, 1 600	1.37 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.93 (6H, s, NMe ₂), 4.93 (2H, AB q, J _{AB} 14.0 Hz, CH ₂), 5.33 (1H, s, CH), 6.53-7.79 (19H, m, ArH)
4b	40	205-6	1 720, 1 600	2.04 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.90 (6H, s, NMe ₂), 4.42 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.93 (1H, s, CH), 6.44-7.55 (19H, m, ArH)
3c	72	184-5	1 715, 1 595	1.50 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.80 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.40 (1H, s, CH), 6.80-8.20 (19H, m, ArH)
4c	28	167	1 725, 1 600	2.30 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.70 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.10 (1H, s, CH), 6.80-8.20 (19H, m, ArH)
3d	58	179-80	1 725, 1 600	1.49 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.90 (6H, s, NMe ₂), 5.36 (1H, s, CH), 6.50-7.97 (19H, m, ArH)
4d	42	184	1 720, 1 600	2.15 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.80 (6H, s, NMe ₂), 5.10 (1H, s, CH), 6.80-8.20 (19H, m, ArH)

*All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

4-Arylmethylene-2,5'-disubstituted-pyrazolones⁴ (1a-d) and the phenylhydrazonoyl chloride⁵ were prepared following the standard methods.

E- and *Z*-4,5-Dihydrospiro[pyrazoles-5,4'-pyrazolones](3a-d and 4a-d): These were prepared according to the reported procedure⁶. Phenyl hydrazonoyl chloride (0.01 mol) in dry chloroform (25 ml) were added dropwise to stirred solution of 4-arylmethyl-2,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2-phenyl/phenylmethyl-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.01 mol) in dry chloroform (25 ml) at room temperature in anhydrous condition. The stirring was continued for 48-72 h. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was taken up with toluene and the resulting triethylaminehydrochloride (Et₃N.HCl) precipitate was filtered off. The toluene fraction gave two spots on

tlc plate corresponding to two components different from starting materials. The products were fractionated by column chromatography on silica gel and eluted with toluene-ethyl acetate (90 : 10) and recrystallised from ethanol.

Results and Discussion

In the pmr spectral data (Table 1) of *E*-isomers (3a-d), the C-5'-methyl proton lies in the shielding zone of C-4-phenyl ring and therefore occurs high field and low δ value (1.34-1.50), while the hydrogen atom at C-4 is deshielded by the anisotropic effect of C-3'-carbonyl group and resonates at low field and high δ value (5.30-5.40 ppm). Phenylmethyl proton (3a,b) at *N*-2' becomes nonequivalent and resonates as AB quartet (centered around δ 4.92, *J*_{AB} 12.0-14.0 Hz). In *Z*-isomers (4a-d), C-5'-methyl proton (δ 2.04-2.30) and C-4-proton (δ 4.93-5.10) resonates at normal position, while phenylmethyl proton (4a,b) at *N*-2' became equivalent and is observed a singlet at δ 4.60 (4a) and 4.42 (4b).

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